

PTC STANDARTI PARAMENTRLARI VA ULARNING BOSHQA STANDARTLARDAN FARQI HAMDA BOG‘LIQLIGI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola PTC (Photovoltaics for Utility-Scale Applications) test sharoitlarining mohiyati va ularning STC standarti bilan solishtirmadagi ustunliklarini ochib beradi. Mualliflar PTC parametrlarining real ish sharoitlariga yaqinligi, fotoelektrik modullarning foydali ish koeffitsienti, harorat koeffitsienti, va test natijalarining mustaqil laboratoriyalar tomonidan baholanish tartiblarini tahlil qilgan. Maqolada PTC/STC nisbati orqali modul sifati va samaradorligini aniqlash usullari, shuningdek, brendli va arzon modullar o‘rtasidagi farqlar yoritilgan. Bu yondashuv quyosh panellari tanlovida yanada aniq qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: PTC standarti, PVUSA sharoitlari, harorat koeffitsienti, real ish samaradorligi, foydali ish koeffitsienti, quvvat tahlili, STC bilan solishtirish, modul sinovlari, GoSolarCalifornia, PTC/STC nisbati.

PTC – bu Photovoltaics for Utility-Scale Applications (PVUSA) Test Conditions degan iboraning qisqartmasi bo‘lib, quyosh panellarining (fotoelektrik modullarning) ishlash samaradorligini baholashda ishlatiladigan standart sinov sharoitlaridan biridir. Bu standart AQShda ishlab chiqilgan va real ish sharoitlariga yaqinroq bo‘lgan qiymatlarni beradi¹.

¹ IEC 61853-1:2011. Photovoltaic (PV) modules – Performance testing and energy rating – Part 1: Irradiance and temperature performance measurements and power rating. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), Geneva.

PTC shartlari yanada realoq hisoblanadi. Biroq, barcha ishlab chiqaruvchilar ham modul parametrlarini PTC uchun ko'rsatavermaydi. Odatda PTC AQSh fotoenergetika bozori uchun ishlab chiqarilgan modullar uchun ko'rsatiladi (1-rasm).

250 WATT
ND-250QCS
Module output cables: 12 AWG PV Wire (per UL Subject 4703)

ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Maximum Power (Pmax)*	250 W
Tolerance of Pmax	+5%/-0%
PTC Rating	223.6 W
Type of Cell	Polycrystalline silicon
Cell Configuration	60 in series
Open Circuit Voltage (Voc)	38.3 V
Maximum Power Voltage (Vpm)	29.8 V
Short Circuit Current (Isc)	8.90 A
Maximum Power Current (Ipm)	8.40 A
Module Efficiency (%)	15.3%
Maximum System (DC) Voltage	600 V (UL)/1000V (IEC)
Series Fuse Rating	15 A

1-rasm. PTC sharoitida quvvat qiymati ko'rsatilgan fotoelektrik moduli yorlig'i

PTC sharoiti sinov parametrlari yoki PVUSA (*Photovoltaics for Utility Systems Applications*) Test Conditions, STCga qaraganda real sharoitlarga yaqinroq bo'lgan shartlarda quyosh panellarini sinash natijalariga to'g'ri keladi. PTC sharoitlarida yoritilganlik 1000 W/m^2 ga teng deb olinadi, lekin unda harorat STCdagi kabi quyosh elementining emas balki atrof-muhit haroratini nazarda tutiladi. Panellar yer sirtidan 10 m balandlikda joylashgan bo'lishi, havo harorati $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ va shamol tezligi 1 m/s bo'lishi kerak².

PTClar turli modullarni solishtirish uchun PVUSA (Utility Scale Applications uchun fotovoltaiklar) loyihasi doirasida ishlab chiqilgan.

² King, D.L., Boyson, W.E., Kratochvil, J.A. (2004). Photovoltaic Array Performance Model. Sandia National Laboratories, SAND2004-3535.

Skoplaki, E., & Palyvos, J.A. (2009). On the temperature dependence of photovoltaic module electrical performance: A review of efficiency/power correlations. *Solar Energy*, 83(5), 614–624.

Loyiha doirasida turli ishlab chiqaruvchilarning 800 kW ga yaqin quyosh panellari bir xil sharoitlarda sinovdan o'tkazilgan. Ko'plab iste'molchi va xaridorlar aynan ushbu sinov natijalariga asoslangan holda ish ko'radilar. Zamonaviy modullar uchun bunday ma'lumotlar <https://www.gosolarcalifornia.org> veb-saytida taqdim etiladi (2-rasm).

PTC parametrlari STC dan 10-15% kamroq, bu esa quyosh modullariga real ish sharoitlarining ta'sirini aks ettiradi³.

NOCT sharoiti harorati modulning PTC sharoitida kutiladigan haroratini hisoblash uchun ishlatiladi, so'ngra quvvatning harorati koeffitsientidan (odatda har bir modul uchun texnik xarakteristikalarida keltiriladi) PTC sharoitida modulning umumiy quvvatini hisoblash uchun foydalaniladi. PTC sharoitidagi modulning ish harorati NOCT dan quyidagi formula yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$T_{cell,PTC} = 20 + 1,389 \cdot (NOCT - 20) \cdot (0,9 - \eta)$$

$(0,9 - \eta)$ qiymat modulga yetib keladigan va issiqlikka aylanadigan quyosh energiyasining ulushini bildiradi. Energiyaning taxminan 10% atrofida qismi sirdan akslanadi⁴. Yana bir qismi elektr energiyasiga aylanadi – bu esa fotoelementning foydali funksiyasi hisoblanadi. Elektr energiyasiga aylantirilgan jami energiyaning ushbu ulushi quyosh modulining foydali ish koeffisienti – η ni bildiradi. Modulning F.I.K. ni STC dagi quvvat qiymatlaridan quyidagi formula yordamida hisoblash mumkin:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{STC}/1000 \text{ W/m}^2}{yuza}$$

³ Emery, K. (2011). Solar Photovoltaic Characterization. In: Markvart, T., & Castaner, L. (eds), Practical Handbook of Photovoltaics: Fundamentals and Applications, Elsevier.

⁴ ASTM G173-03(2012). Standard Tables for Reference Solar Spectral Irradiances: Direct Normal and Hemispherical on 37° Tilted Surface. ASTM International.

2-rasm. PV modul sinovlari natijalarini ishlab chiqaruvchilarning ma'lumotlari bilan solishtirish

Agar PTC sharoitlari uchun element harorati aniqlansa, quvvatning harorat koeffitsienti (C_T) yordamida, STC sharoitidagi quvvatdan foydalanib PTC dagi quvvatni quyidagi ifoda yordamida hisoblash mumkin:

$$P_{PTC} = P_{STC} \cdot \frac{1}{C_T(T_{cell,PTC} - 25^{\circ}C)}$$

Bu esa, *California Energy Commission (CEC)* ning GoSolarCalifornia_saytidagi quvvatning aynan o'zidir. Bu qiymat Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlarida mavjud bo'lgan turli xil qayta tiklanadigan energetika uchun subsidiyalar va imtiyozlarga ega bo'lish uchun quyosh batareyalari ishlab chiqargan elektr energiyasini hisoblash uchun ishlatiladi⁵.

2009 yil 1 iyulgacha CEC ishlab chiqaruvchilardan olingan ma'lumotlar asosida PTC qiymatlarini hisoblab chiqqan va e'lon qilib kelgan. Shu tarzda, NOCT, quvvatning harorati koeffitsientlari o'lchangan, keyin qolgan parametrlar ishlab chiqaruvchilar tomonidan taqdim etilgan ma'lumotlarga asoslangan maxsus texnika yordamida baholandi. 2009 yil 1 iyuldan keyin CEC faqat mustaqil laboratoriyalardan

⁵ Green, M.A. (2003). Solar Cells: Operating Principles, Technology, and System Applications. UNSW, Australia.

olingan PTC ma'lumotlarini nashr etadi va ishlab chiqaruvchilardan ma'lumotlarni qabul qilmaydi. Sinov laboratoriyalari yaxshi jihozlangan va yuqori aniqlikda o'lchash sharoitlarini ta'minlash imkoniyatiga ega⁶. Ular taqdim etgan modul sinovlari natijalarini ishlab chiqaruvchilardan olingan eski ma'lumotlar bilan solishtirilganda, ko'pchilik ishlab chiqaruvchilar o'z mahsulotlarining imkoniyatlarini haddan tashqari oshirib yuborishganligi ma'lum bo'ldi. Sinovdan o'tkazilgan 475 moduldan 308 tasi yomon, 51 tasi bir xil va 116 tasi ishlab chiqaruvchilar da'vo qilganidan yaxshiroq natijalar berdi (2-rasm).

O'ngdagi rasmdan ko'rinib turibdiki, 250 W li Sharp ND-250QCS quyosh paneli PTC sharoitida 223,6 W quvvatga ega ekan (1-rasmga qarang). Agar ushbu quyosh panelidan real fotoelektrik tizimda foydalansak, STC da 250 W quvvat hosil qiladigan modulning real sharoitdagi quvvati PTC bo'yicha 223,6 W teng bo'lishini to'g'ri baholash imkonini beradi. Aslini olganda, xuddi STC singari, PTC ham real ish sharoitida kuzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan modul quvvatdan kattaroq ko'rsatkichlarni beradi.

GoSolarCalifornia saytiga qo'shimcha ravishda, ko'plab modullarning PTC bo'yicha ma'lumotlarini [SolarHub](#), [SolarReviews](#) saytlaridan topish mumkin (3-rasm).

Fotoelektrik modulning narxi odatda uning nominal quvvatiga bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, modullarni PTC/STC dagi parametrlari o'zaro nisbati asosida solishtirish foydali bo'ladi. Yaxshi va sifatli modullarda bu nisbat 88% dan yuqori. Agar PTC/STC 0,88 dan kichik bo'lsa, bunday modulni xarid qilmaslikni maslahat beriladi.

PTC dagi quvvat tahlil natijalari qilish shuni ko'rsatadiki, odatda (lekin har doim ham emas) polikristal fotoelektrik modullar monokristalli modullarga qaraganda kichikroq PTC/STC koeffisientiga ega. Bu shuni anglatadiki, issiq ob-havoda aksariyat

⁶ Honsberg, C., & Bowden, S. PV Education Website, <https://www.pveducation.org>.
Messenger, R., & Ventre, J. (2010). Photovoltaic Systems Engineering (3rd Edition). CRC Press.

monokristalli modullar kamroq quvvatni yo'qotadi va shunga mos ravishda ko'proq elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqaradi.

The screenshot shows the SolarHub website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation tabs for 'PV MODULES', 'ACPV', 'INVERTERS', and 'MANUFACTURERS'. A sidebar on the left allows filtering by various attributes such as Manufacturer, Power at STC (W), Cell Type, Connector Type, Frame Color, Backsheet Color, BIPV, CSI Status, and In Production. The main content area displays a table of 20 items, all from the manufacturer 'Soltech'. The table columns are 'Manufacturer', 'Model', 'Power (STC)', and 'Cell Type'. The items listed include models like 1STH-215-P, 1STH-220-P, 1STH-225-P, 1STH-230-P, 1STH-235-WH, 1STH-240-P, 1STH-240-WH, 1STH-240WH, 1STH-245-P, 1STH-245-WH, 1STH-250-P, 1STH-250-WH, 1STH-335-WH, 1STH-340-WH, 1STH-345-WH, 1STH-350-WH, 1STH-FRL-4H-245-M60-BLK, 1STH-FRL-4H-250-M60-BLK, 1STH-FRL-4H-255-M60-BLK, and 1STH-FRL-4H-260-M60-BLK. The power (STC) values range from 215 to 350 W, and cell types include Poly and Mono.

3-rasm. Modul ma'lumotlari bo'yicha SolarHub saytidan olingan namuna

1-jadval

Ba'zi brend fotoelektrik modullar uchun PTC/STC ning o'zaro nisbatlari

Model	Ishlab chiqaruvchi	Turi	STC, W	PTC, W	PTC/STC, %
CS5A-210M	Canadian Solar	Mono	210	190,8	90,86
YL250P-29b	Yingli	Poli	250	226,2	90,48
YL250C-30b	Yingli	Mono	250	230,3	92,12
JAP6-60-250	JA Solar	Poli	250	222,9	89,16
SF-220P x-tra	Hanwha Solar One	Poli	250	226,02	90,4
HSE300-72P	ChinaLand	Poli	300	265,5	88,5
HSE300-72M	ChinaLand	Mono	300	270,6	90,2
IM60C3-250	Motech Industries	Poli	250	228,4	91,36
XS72C3-300	Motech Industries	Mono	300	267,9	89,3

*Xanchjou Zhejiang University Sunny Energy Science & Technology – Suntellite brendi ostida Xitoydagi modul ishlab chiqaruvchilardan biri.

Shuningdek, sinov natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, brendli modullar odatda yuqori PTC/STC ko'rsatkichlariga ega. Ba'zi modullar uchun PTC/STC ning o'zaro nisbatlari quyidagi jadvalda ko'rsatilgan (1-jadval).

Jadvalda keltirilgan ushbu modular ichida nisbatan kichik koeffisientga ega bo'lganlarining tannarxi past bo'lishini hisobga hisobga olgan holda, bunday quyosh panellari ko'plab import qiluvchi davlatlarda ishlatilmasligini yuqori ehtimollik bilan aytish mumkin.

Umuman olganda, na PTC va na STC real sharoitlarda modul quvvatining o'zgarishiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarning barchasini aks ettirmaydi. Quyosh elektr stantsiyasining ishlashiga ta'sir qiluvchi boshqa omillarni hisobga olish kerak. O'tkazgich kabellar, invertor, kontroller va boshqa shu kabi fotoelektrik tizim elementlaridagi yo'qotishlarni ham hisobga olish zarur. Shuningdek, vaqt o'tishi bilan quyosh panellarining normal degradatsiyasi, shuningdek, chang, loyqa, modullarning haddan tashqari qizishi yoki ularning soyalanishi, ketma-ket ulangan modullarning turlicha quvvatga ega bo'lishi kabi omillar tufayli quvvatning pasayishi kuzatiladi. Ushbu omillarning ta'siri yil fasliga, geografik joylashuvga, o'rnatish usuliga, panellarning azimuti va qiyaligiga kabilarga qarab farq qilishi mumkin.

Bundan tashqari, PTC standartining muhimligi: haqiqiy samaradorlik – quyosh panellarining real ish faoliyatini baholashga yordam beradi; soliqlash va subsidiyalar – AQShda ayrim shtatlarda soliq imtiyozlari yoki subsidiya dasturlari PTC reytingiga asoslangan bo'ladi; investorlar uchun aniqlik – uzoq muddatli ishlab chiqarish prognozlarini aniqlashtirishda foydali.

Adabiyotlar:

1. IEC 61853-1:2011. Photovoltaic (PV) modules – Performance testing and energy rating – Part 1: Irradiance and temperature performance measurements and power rating. International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), Geneva.
2. King, D.L., Boyson, W.E., Kratochvil, J.A. (2004). Photovoltaic Array Performance Model. Sandia National Laboratories, SAND2004-3535.

3. Skoplaki, E., & Palyvos, J.A. (2009). On the temperature dependence of photovoltaic module electrical performance: A review of efficiency/power correlations. *Solar Energy*, 83(5), 614–624.
4. Emery, K. (2011). Solar Photovoltaic Characterization. In: Markvart, T., & Castaner, L. (eds), *Practical Handbook of Photovoltaics: Fundamentals and Applications*, Elsevier.
5. ASTM G173-03(2012). Standard Tables for Reference Solar Spectral Irradiances: Direct Normal and Hemispherical on 37° Tilted Surface. ASTM International.
6. Green, M.A. (2003). *Solar Cells: Operating Principles, Technology, and System Applications*. UNSW, Australia.
7. Honsberg, C., & Bowden, S. PV Education Website, <https://www.pveducation.org>.
8. Messenger, R., & Ventre, J. (2010). *Photovoltaic Systems Engineering (3rd Edition)*. CRC Press.